

1 **Protocol-Effects of progressive multimodal resistance training with varied muscle**
2 **actions and range of motion on bone mineral density in osteopenic older women: a pilot**
3 **study**

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1 **Summary**

2 **Background / Objectives**

3 Resistance training has been shown to be an effective strategy for improving bone health in
4 individuals with osteopenia; however, programs based on high external loads may not be
5 appropriate or safe for all older women. In this context, alternative approaches that modulate
6 the mechanical stimulus through prescription variables such as muscle action type and joint
7 range of motion may allow the generation of relevant osteogenic adaptations with lower
8 external mechanical demands.

9 This pilot study examined the effect of a progressive multimodal resistance training program
10 on bone mineral density (BMD) in osteopenic women.

11 **Methods**

12 A prospective, non-randomized pilot study with two parallel groups (experimental and
13 control) will be conducted. Twenty older women diagnosed with osteopenia will participate
14 and will be allocated to groups based on availability criteria.

15 Following ethical approval and the acquisition of written informed consent, participants in
16 the experimental group will complete a 16-week progressive multimodal resistance training
17 program with planned variation in muscle action type and joint range of motion. The control
18 group will continue with their usual aerobic-based physical activity program.

19 Bone mineral density of the lumbar spine and femoral neck will be assessed before and after
20 the intervention period using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA). Data analysis will
21 follow an estimation-based approach, complemented by robust and Bayesian methods, which
22 are appropriate for pilot studies with small sample sizes.

23 **Expected Outcomes**

24 It is expected that this multimodal resistance training program will be feasible and safe for
25 older women with osteopenia and will produce favorable changes in bone mineral density
26 at the lumbar spine and femoral neck compared with the control group. Additionally, the
27 results are anticipated to allow the estimation of preliminary effect sizes to inform the
28 design of a future large-scale randomized controlled trial.

29 **Significance / Implications**

30 This study will provide preliminary evidence on a potentially safer and more adaptable
31 resistance training approach for older women with osteopenia, based on the modulation of
32 muscle action type and range of motion. The expected findings may inform clinical and
33 community-based strategies aimed at osteoporosis prevention and optimization of exercise
34 prescription in aging populations, as well as serve as a methodological foundation for future
35 randomized controlled trials.

36 **Keywords**

37 Multimodal resistance training; osteopenia; older women; bone mineral density; muscle
38 action; range of motion; pilot study.

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1 **Rationale / Background**

2 Aging constitutes an intrinsic biological process characterized by a progressive decline in the
3 function of multiple organ systems, including the musculoskeletal system (Cannataro et al.,
4 2021; Liao et al., 2021). In women, bone mass loss may reach up to 40%, beginning as early
5 as the third decade of life (Azzolino et al., 2021; Hirschfeld et al., 2017). However, this
6 process does not occur uniformly and is modulated by multiple biological, hormonal, and
7 mechanical factors.

8 From a pathophysiological perspective, the age-related decline in bone repair capacity is
9 primarily explained by three interrelated mechanisms: osteocyte apoptosis, reduced osteocyte
10 density, and the progressive accumulation of microdamage within the bone matrix (Calvi,
11 2019; Weaver & Peacock, 2019; Yao et al., 2024). These processes are further exacerbated
12 by mineralization of the lacunar spaces (micropetrosis), which impairs canalicular fluid flow
13 and microdamage detection, thereby critically compromising the regenerative capacity of
14 bone tissue (Hemmatian et al., 2017; Jilka & O'Brien, 2016; Milovanovic & Busse, 2023).
15 Additionally, estrogen deficiency associated with the postmenopausal period may accelerate
16 bone loss through mechanisms that are partially independent of chronological aging (El
17 Miedany, 2022; Padilla Colon et al., 2018).

18 Osteopenia and osteoporosis represent a global public health problem with a substantial
19 epidemiological and clinical burden (Salari et al., 2021). It is estimated that osteoporosis
20 affects 19.7% of the global population, whereas osteopenia reaches a prevalence of 40.4%,
21 being even more frequent than osteoporosis in developed countries (Xiao et al., 2022). In the
22 United States, 19.6% of women over the age of 50 have osteoporosis, while 51.5% present
23 with osteopenia (Sarafrazi et al., 2021). In Latin America, although data remain limited, a
24 high prevalence of reduced bone mass in older women has been reported, with rates of 50%
25 in Argentina, 59% in Mexico, and fracture rates in Brazil suggesting an osteopenia
26 prevalence between 10.5% and 17% (Clark et al., 2013). In Colombia, the situation is
27 particularly concerning, with a sustained increase over the past decade and reported
28 prevalences of 34.46% for osteoporosis and 45.14% for osteopenia among women aged 60
29 years or older (Espitia-De-La-Hoz, 2021). Postmenopausal women exhibit significantly
30 greater susceptibility, with an osteopenia prevalence of 48.55% compared with
31 premenopausal women (Fan et al., 2024).

32 Resistance training has been shown to be an effective intervention for improving bone
33 mineral density in older adults (O'Bryan et al., 2022; Watson et al., 2018). Nevertheless, in
34 aging populations, the implementation of programs based on high external loads may be
35 limited by an increased risk of injury and the occurrence of delayed-onset muscle soreness,
36 phenomena that may be exacerbated by age-related declines in recovery capacity (Sousa et
37 al., 2014). These considerations highlight the need for carefully designed training programs
38 that are adapted to the physiological limitations of the geriatric population (Cannataro et al.,
39 2022; Ciolac & Rodrigues-da-Silva, 2016; Collado-Mateo et al., 2021).

40 In this context, recent research has explored a variety of training modalities aimed at
41 improving bone mineral density in older women, including resistance training with external
42 loads, elastic bands, whole-body vibration, and aquatic exercise, integrated within strength

1 and cardiorespiratory exercise programs (Banitalebi et al., 2021; Borba-Pinheiro et al., 2016;
2 ElDeeb & Abdel-Aziem, 2020; Ghosal & Bandyopadhyay, 2020; Moreira et al., 2014;
3 Nicholson et al., 2015). These interventions have systematically manipulated classical
4 exercise prescription variables such as intensity (expressed as a percentage of one-repetition
5 maximum or repetition maximums), volume, duration, frequency, density, load progression,
6 vibration parameters, postural complexity, and perceived exertion (Banitalebi et al., 2021;
7 Borba-Pinheiro et al., 2016; de Oliveira et al., 2019; ElDeeb & Abdel-Aziem, 2020; Ghosal
8 & Bandyopadhyay, 2020; Moreira et al., 2014; Nicholson et al., 2015).

9 Despite the availability of guidelines and multiple strategies for controlling training intensity
10 in older adults, the potential of muscle action type and joint range of motion as primary
11 prescriptive variables remains largely unexplored. These variables may represent safer and
12 more adaptable alternatives to high-load protocols, particularly in older women with
13 osteopenia, who face an increased risk of injury and reduced tolerance to mechanical stress.
14 Accordingly, the present non-randomized pilot study is designed to preliminarily evaluate
15 the potential effectiveness of a 16-week progressive multimodal resistance training program
16 that systematically manipulates muscle action type and range of motion. The findings from
17 this study will be used to inform methodological design, sample size estimation, and key
18 parameters for a future large-scale definitive clinical trial aimed at improving bone health in
19 this vulnerable population.

20 **Study objective**

21 This pilot study aims to examine the effect of a progressive multimodal resistance training
22 program on bone mineral density (BMD) in older women with osteopenia.

23 **Study hypotheses**

24 **Primary hypothesis**

25 Participation in a 16-week progressive multimodal resistance training program, based on the
26 manipulation of muscle action type and range of motion, will result in greater improvements
27 in bone mineral density at the lumbar spine and femoral neck in older women with osteopenia
28 compared with a control group.

29 **Null hypothesis**

30 There will be no differences in changes in bone mineral density at the lumbar spine or femoral
31 neck between older women with osteopenia who participate in the multimodal resistance
32 training program and those assigned to the control group.

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1 Trial design

2 This will be a two-arm repeated-measures non-randomized pilot study to be conducted in
 3 osteopenic older women. The study will be reported in accordance with the Consolidated
 4 Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) extension to pilot and feasibility trials (Eldridge
 5 et al., 2016). We will evaluate the effects of a 16-week progressive multimodal resistance
 6 training program involving varied muscle actions and range of motion (ROM) on bone
 7 mineral density in Colombian women diagnosed with osteopenia (Figure 1).

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Figure 1. Experimental design of the study. DXA: Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry.

10 Participants

11 Older women from a municipality in southwestern Colombia (San Pedro, Valle del Cauca)
 12 will be recruited for this pilot trial, which will be conducted as part of an undergraduate thesis
 13 project in a physical education program at a public university [details omitted for double-
 14 anonymized peer review]. Participants will be identified through community outreach efforts
 15 and informational sessions held at local health centers.

16 Eligible participants will be aged 60–70 years, will have a confirmed diagnosis of osteopenia
 17 via dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) (T-score between -1.0 and -2.5), and will not
 18 have participated in a structured training program in the preceding six months.

19 Exclusion criteria will include: i) osteoporosis (T-score < -2.5); advanced cardiovascular
 20 disease (heart failure class II–IV [NYHA], recent myocardial infarction [<6 months],
 21 unstable angina); severe renal failure (eGFR < 30 mL/min/1.73 m²); alcohol, psychoactive
 22 substance, or tobacco addiction; implants or foreign devices in the measurement area; active
 23 malignancy requiring treatment; endocrine or metabolic disorders (type 1 or type 2 diabetes,
 24 thyroid or parathyroid disease, Paget's disease of bone); recent (<1 month) barium
 25 examination or contrast injection for CT or radioisotope studies; and use of medications
 26 affecting bone metabolism (bisphosphonates, SERMs, hormone replacement therapy,
 27 corticosteroids, aromatase inhibitors, anticonvulsants, anticoagulants, antiresorptives, bone-
 28 forming agents, anabolic steroids, or androgens).

1 Exit criteria will include participant withdrawal, adverse effects preventing continuation,
2 repeated absenteeism, development of exclusionary medical conditions, or changes in
3 medication. All older women will be thoroughly informed about the research objectives, as
4 well as the associated risks and benefits. Subsequently, they will sign an informed consent
5 form in accordance with the ethical guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (World
6 Medical, 2013).

7 **Setting**

8 The study will be conducted at a university-affiliated sports science and physical activity
9 center [details omitted for double-anonymized peer review], equipped with strength-training
10 machines and exercise tools (dumbbells, benches, medicine balls, lightweight discs), and will
11 be supervised by professionals in sports science, medicine, and physiotherapy. A non-
12 randomized pilot design will be selected due to logistical and feasibility (budget) constraints,
13 including limited sample availability and resource allocation.

14 **Intervention Procedures**

15 The 16-week exercise intervention will include multi-joint machine exercises (hack squat
16 [Pure Hack Squat, Technogym, Cesena, Italy] and horizontal leg press [Pro2 Seated Leg
17 Press, Life Fitness, Chicago, IL, USA]) alongside functional free-weight exercises designed
18 to simulate activities of daily living.

19 The progressive multimodal resistance training program with varied muscle actions and
20 ROM will be implemented three times per week (non-consecutive days with four participants
21 per session) in four phases: i) Phase 1 (Weeks 1–4): Concentric (2 s) and assisted eccentric
22 (1 s) actions (velocity ratio [VE] 2:1) on hack squat and leg press machine exercises.
23 Horizontal training method (all sets of one exercise completed before progression); ii) Phase
24 2 (Weeks 5–8): Concentric-isometric actions (VE 2:3); eccentric actions excluded for initial
25 progression (LaStayo et al., 2014); iii) Phase 3 (Weeks 9–12): Autonomous eccentric actions
26 (VE 2:4); and iv) Phase 4 (Weeks 13–16): Double sets with moderate ROM and vertical
27 training (alternating exercises without rest; VE 1:2).

28 ROM will be standardized using a digital goniometer (Baseline 12-1027 Absolute Axis 360
29 Degree, Dedham, MS, USA). For the two machine exercises, very limited ROM (#1) will be
30 defined as 120°–110° at the tibiofemoral joint and 125°–100° at the coxofemoral joint,
31 ensuring greater spinal protection. Limited ROM (#2) will range from 109°–100°
32 (tibiofemoral) and 99°–80° (coxofemoral), while moderate ROM (#3) will be set at 99°–90°
33 (tibiofemoral) and 79°–60° (coxofemoral).

34 The program also will incorporate functional exercises simulating activities of daily living,
35 such as chair stands, object retrieval, and step climbing, using adjustable dumbbells (5–12
36 lbs), low-height benches (10–30 cm), and medicine balls (2–10 lbs). Exercise complexity
37 will progress from single-joint to multi-joint movements (Table 1).

38 Exercises simulating activities of daily living will use adjustable dumbbells (Bowflex, 5–12
39 lbs), low-height benches (10–30 cm), medicine balls (TRX, 2–10 lbs), and lightweight discs
40 (Eleiko, 5–10 lbs). These exercises will replicate fundamental and instrumental activities of
41 daily living, including chair stands, object manipulation (carrying, retrieving, reaching), and

- 1 step negotiation (ascending/descending). Exercise progression will follow two dimensions:
2 complexity (advancing from single-joint to multi-joint movements) and difficulty (increased
3 via greater loads or elevated bench heights).
- 4 Baseline performance will be established using unloaded machine exercises (platform weight
5 = 44 lbs for hack squat and leg press), with emphasis on proper technique, individualized
6 ROM parameters, and controlled muscle action durations (concentric, eccentric, isometric).
7 Participants will log exercises and difficulties post-session. Attendance and protocol
8 adherence will be tracked. Motivational strategies will include goal setting, weekly feedback,
9 and monthly interviews.
- 10 The control group will participate in a regular dance therapy program (3×/week) in the same
11 facilities. This program will consist of a 10-min warm-up (walking + joint mobility), a 30-
12 min low-impact dance (60–70% max heart rate and the use of rating perceived scale), and a
13 10-min cooldown (walking + stretching). Dance will be chosen as an active control to match
14 social and motivational engagement while minimizing osteogenic stimulus.

Table 1. 16-Week Progressive Multimodal Resistance Training Program

Phase (Muscle action)	Phase 1 - Concentric action				Phase 2 - Concentric-isometric action				Phase 3 - Concentric-eccentric action				Phase 4 - Concentric-eccentric action			
Month	May				June				July				August			
Week	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Start and end dates	2–7 May	9– 13 May	16– 20 May	23– 27 May o	30 May 3 June	6– 10 June	13– 17 June	20– 24 June	27– 1 July	4–8 July	11– 15 July	18– 22 July	25– 29 July	1–5 August t	8–12 August t	15-19 August t
Sessions per week	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Average session volume (min)	45'	45'	45'	45'	50'	50'	50'	45'	50'	50'	50'	45'	55'	55'	55'	45'
Total weekly volume (min)	135'	135'	135'	135'	150'	150'	150'	135'	150'	150'	150'	135'	165'	165'	165'	135'
Warm-up (5') and cool down (10')	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'	45'
Functional exercises with light loads in low-complexity domestic work activities	3/21 , (7')	3/21 , (7')	3/21 , (7')	3/21' , (7')	1/8' , (8')	1/8' , (8')	1/8' , (8')	1/6' , (6')								
Functional exercises with light loads in moderate-complexity domestic work activities					2/16 , (8')	2/16 , (8')	2/16 , (8')	2/14 , (7')	3/24 , (8')	3/24 , (8')	3/24 , (8')	3/21 , (7')	3/27 , (9')	3/27' , (9')	3/27' , (9')	3/21' , (7')
Multi-joint exercises on machines under passive stability conditions																
Individual exercises (horizontal method)	69' (23)	69' (23)	30' (10)	30' (10')	81' (27)	36' (12)	39' (13)	30' (10)								
Number of exercises/series/repetitions	5/2 6-8	6/3 6-8	3/2 8-10	2/2 8-10	6/2 4-6	3/2 4-6	3/2 4-6	2/2 4-5	6/2 4-6	3/2 4-6	3/2 4-6	2/2 4-6	6/2 4-6	3/2 6-8	3/2 6-8	2/2 4-6
Range of motion	1	1	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Execution speed (seconds) / Rest interval between series (min)	2/1	2 /1.0	2/1. 0		2-2/ 1.5	2-3/ 1.5	2-3/ 1.5	2-2/ 1.5	2-2/ 1.5	2-2/ 1.5	2-2/ 1.5	2-2/ 1.5	2-4/ 2.0	2-4/ 2.0	2-4/ 2.0	2-2/ 2.0

Double series exercises (vertical method)	39' (13)	39' (13')	45' (15)	45' (15)	39' (13)			
Number of exercises/double series/repetitions	4/2 6-8	3/2 6-8	4/2 4-6	4/2 4-6	4/2 4-5	4/2 6-8	4/2 6-8	4/1 6-8
Range of motion	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	3
Execution speed (seconds) / Rest interval between double series (min)	2/2	2/2	2-3/ 3.0	2-3/ 3.0	2-2/ 3.0	1-1/ 3.0	1-1/ 3.0	1-1/ 3.0
Triple series exercises (vertical method)								
Number of exercises/triple series/repetitions						6/2 6-8	6/2 6-8	6/1 6-8
Range of motion						3	3	3
Execution speed (seconds) / Rest interval (between exercises - between triple series) (min)						1-2/ 1-4	1-2/ 1-4	1-2/ 1-4

- 1
- 2 Range of motion: #1 is very limited; #2 is Limited; and #3 is Moderate. Sequence of muscle actions in exercise execution: concentric action – eccentric
- 3 action (e.g., 2-2).

1 Protocol adherence will be defined as participants attending at least 90% of the intervention
2 sessions, while participant retention will be considered acceptable if at least 85% of women
3 remain in the study until its completion (Hakestad et al., 2015). Safety will be evaluated by
4 the absence of serious adverse events throughout the intervention period.

5 **Outcomes**

6 As a primary outcome, bone mineral density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) at the femoral neck and lumbar spine
7 will be measured via dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) (Lunar Prodigy Advance, GE
8 Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA) using TBS iNsight softw Mesinovic et al., 2025are.
9 Participants will be instructed to avoid calcium intake 24 hours prior, wear loose clothing,
10 and remove jewelry. For the lumbar spine measurement, participants will be positioned
11 supine with legs bent on a support to reduce lumbar lordosis, and the L1–L4 vertebrae will
12 be scanned. For the femoral neck measurement, the right hip will be internally rotated (15–
13 30°), with the minor trochanter excluded from view. Appropriate patient positioning will be
14 based on previous clinical recommendations to estimate bone mineral density using the DXA
15 method (Themeli & Triantafyllopoulos, 2021). Two certified technicians (with more than 7
16 years of experience) will independently analyze the scans to minimize errors. Results will be
17 compared to NHANES III reference data for T- and Z-scores, considering age- and sex-
18 specific values.

19 **Sample size**

20 This study will be conceived as a pilot trial. The sample size of 20 participants (10 per group)
21 will be based on practical constraints (convenience sampling) and will be aligned with
22 previous pilot studies on resistance training in older adults, such as those by Balachandran et
23 al. (Balachandran et al., 2014) ($n = 21$). While no formal a priori power analysis will be
24 conducted, this sample size is typical for early-phase feasibility trials.

25 **Allocation**

26 Participants will be non-randomly allocated to either the experimental or control group based
27 on availability and scheduling constraints. To reduce measurement bias, evaluators will be
28 blinded to group assignment. Both groups will receive equal session frequency (three times
29 per week) and professional supervision to enhance procedural consistency and reduce
30 performance bias.

31 **Statistical analysis**

32 Descriptive statistics will be reported as mean and standard deviation (SD) with the
33 corresponding 95% confidence interval (95% CI). Based on current recommendations to
34 improve data analysis practices (Martin & Teste, 2022), we will employ an estimation,
35 robust, and Bayesian approach, consistent with methodologies detailed in prior studies
36 involving older adult populations (Bonilla et al., 2021; Vargas-Molina et al., 2022). To
37 determine statistical significance, we will examine the 95% CIs for the difference between
38 the mean change scores ($\Delta = \text{Week 16} - \text{Week 0}$). If the 95% CI excludes zero, the difference
39 will attain significance at the $p < 0.05$ level. Effect size will be calculated as unbiased
40 Cohen's d (d_{unb}), with its magnitude serving as the primary indicator of clinical
41 significance. Following established benchmarks, a value of ≤ 0.2 will be considered small,

1 0.5 moderate, and ≥ 0.8 large (Rosenthal, 1996). In addition, a minimal clinically important
2 difference will be defined as a change of $+0.03 \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ for any bone section, as recommended
3 for non-obese postmenopausal women (Briot et al., 2018; Dorilleau et al., 2024). Gardner-
4 Altman estimation plots will be generated to display paired data before and after the
5 intervention. In addition, we will apply Yuen-Dixon's paired-sample t-test as a robust method
6 suitable for small sample sizes. This approach employs 20% trimmed means (μ_t) and
7 incorporates bootstrapping to enhance Type I error control, particularly for skewed data
8 distributions. Finally, the Yuen test for independent groups will be used for the pairwise
9 comparisons of the Δ between groups. Findings will be confirmed with frequentist and
10 Bayesian ANCOVA adjusting for baseline values. We will estimate the likelihood ratio (also
11 called the Bayes Factor [BF]), which is the most widely accepted measure to quantify how
12 much evidence a data set provides for a hypothesis. Statistical analyses will be performed
13 using the Wilcox' Robust Statistics (WRS2) package and the JASP module 'jsq' within the
14 R statistical computing environment (R Core Team, 2017).

15 **Ethical approval and considerations**

16 This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Central University of Valle del
17 Cauca (PI-1300-50.2-2024-08). All procedures were conducted in accordance with the
18 principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and its subsequent amendments. Written informed
19 consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study.

20 **Trial registration**

21 This study was prospectively registered in the open-access repository Zenodo prior to the
22 initiation of participant recruitment. The full study protocol is publicly available under the
23 Digital Object Identifier (DOI): 10.5281/zenodo.18487882.

24 This registration aims to ensure methodological transparency, traceability of the study
25 design, and public access to information related to the study objectives, methods, and planned
26 analyses.

27 **Data management and confidentiality**

28 The datasets that will be generated and analyzed during the present study will not be publicly
29 available due to ethical considerations and the need to protect participant confidentiality.
30 However, fully anonymized individual-level data, together with the analysis scripts used to
31 generate the results, will be made available upon reasonable request to the corresponding
32 author for purposes of academic verification and scientific reproducibility.

33 **Dissemination plan**

34 The findings of this study will be disseminated through publication in peer-reviewed
35 scientific journals and presentation at national conferences.

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1 This study was funded by the Central University of Valle del Cauca (UCEVA). The funding
 2 institution had no role in the study design, data collection and analysis, interpretation of the
 3 results, or manuscript preparation.

4 **Conflicts of Interest**

5 D.A.B. has conducted academic-sponsored research in sport and exercise sciences, serves as
 6 an advisor to the NSCA Colombia Board, and has received honoraria related to the sale of
 7 muscular performance and body composition equipment, as well as for speaking
 8 engagements in exercise sciences at international conferences and private courses. All other
 9 authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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